

The COVID-19 Vaccination – A Crime Against Humanity?

Abstract

Much has been said about the COVID-19 pandemic. To this day, many people insist on calling everything COVID-related "a crime against humanity" or even "a war crime". It is undisputed that many mistakes were committed. Indeed, it is arguable that literally every policy decision around the pandemic was a mistake and that doing nothing would have worked better. The universal lockdowns are one example as they went against initial epidemiological recommendations from the World Health Organization ([WHO], 2020). Some of the mistakes might have been criminal. Some of them might have violated human rights. Yet, not all of them could have been crimes against humanity and/or war crimes. The war crimes charge falls immediately because, while the COVID situation might have been many things, it was not a war. Calling anything and everything a crime against humanity ironically helps those who have actually committed such crimes by creating too much noise to understand what is happening.

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What Is a Crime Against Humanity?

A crime against humanity is:

For the purpose of this Statute, ‘crime against humanity’ means any of the following acts when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population, with knowledge of the attack:

(a) Murder;

(b) Extermination;

(c) Enslavement;

(d) Deportation or forcible transfer of population;

(e) Imprisonment or other severe deprivation of physical liberty in violation of fundamental rules of international law;

(f) Torture;

(g) Rape, sexual slavery, enforced prostitution, forced pregnancy, enforced sterilization, or any other form of sexual violence of comparable gravity;

(h) Persecution against any identifiable group or collectivity on political, racial, national, ethnic, cultural, religious, gender (...), or other grounds that are universally recognized as impermissible under international law, in connection with any act referred to in this paragraph or any crime within the jurisdiction of the Court;

(i) Enforced disappearance of persons;

(j) The crime of apartheid;

(k) Other inhumane acts of a similar character intentionally causing great suffering, or serious injury to body or to mental or physical health.

(International Criminal Court [ICC], 2021, Article 7)

Many people focus on the excess deaths following the COVID pandemic, and many blame the so-called vaccines for that. More specifically, this means people accuse the "people in power" of extermination: "the intentional infliction of conditions of life, inter alia the deprivation of access to food and medicine, calculated to bring about the destruction of part of a population" (ICC, 2021, Art. 7). For this charge to be accurate and legally binding, 4 criteria must be satisfied:

1. There is/was an organized system;
2. the system caused large-scale human death beyond what was reasonably unavoidable;
3. the constituents of the system knew or were willfully ignorant,
4. and contributed to the system's operation.

Simply said, if you contributed to a system that caused countless, preventable deaths while being aware or willfully ignorant, then you have committed a crime against humanity, more precisely in this case, extermination. And, yes, this is simple. Whether you are responsible for a crime against humanity, is not supposed to be mysterious.

Furthermore, humanity has quickly forgotten its history. The Nuremberg Trials establish that, when you commit a crime against humanity (United Nations [UN], 2005):

- "I just did my job", does not matter.
- "I just followed orders", does not matter.
- "My actions were legal under my national jurisdiction", does not matter.
- "I was pardoned", does not matter.

"Life is complicated", is also not a legal excuse. People seem to think that pardons or domestic amnesties matter in this case, but they do not. If political pardons would count, then any country could commit crimes against humanity, and then just pardon itself. That would be incoherent, and so pardons are irrelevant under international law.

What Are COVID “Vaccines”?

So, was the implementation of the COVID "vaccines" a crime against humanity, more precisely extermination? Firstly, we need to understand what COVID "vaccines" even are. There are 4 recognized types deployed for civilian use:

1. viral-vector (AstraZeneca, Johnson & Johnson, Sputnik V, Sputnik Light, CanSino)
2. mRNA (Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna)
3. inactivated virus (Sinopharm, Sinovac, Covaxin, Valneva, QazVac)
4. protein-subunit (Novavax, Abdala, Soberana 02, Sanofi)

There does not seem to be clear information on their taxonomy or how prevalent each type of vaccine is, denoting an absence of consolidated public information. A few recognized facts are that the viral-vector type has the largest global reach of 182 countries (Rashedi et al., 2021), mRNA type has been especially used in high-income nations, and the inactivated virus type especially in lower income nations. The 4th category is quite rare. There is technically a 5th category, DNA vaccines, however, the only known case is ZyCoV-D which was deployed in India within a limited scope (Zhou et al., 2026). The first three ones are dominant.

The reason I use scare quotes around COVID "vaccines", is that most people do not know what vaccines are. Most people do not seem to have any idea, while a minority is vaguely aware that vaccines are inactivated viruses transmitted with an agent in the body so that the body can build antibodies. This definition only properly incorporates type 3 and maybe type 4. The fact that most people are completely unaware what types 1 and 2 are, proves beyond any reasonable doubt the failure of public education and information, if nothing else. According to literal common knowledge, types 1 and 2 are not even vaccines, so misunderstanding was foreseeable, if nothing else. What is the difference between COVID vaccination and genetic therapy? Was the differentiation reasonable or arbitrary? These are questions that must be answered before we can ask whether their implementation was criminal, because if one accuses another of a crime, one must specify what the crime is.

For the sake of simplicity and continuation, this text simply assumes that all recognized COVID "vaccines" are in fact vaccines. Even so, they are still not the same, and another essential distinction must be made here: Is the accusation that all vaccine

implementations are crimes against humanity, or only the COVID ones? Assuming it is the latter, then the accusation is constrained to types 1 and 2, and maybe 5, since types 3 and 4 are traditionally accepted technologies with decades of prior civilian use. Types 1, 2 and 5 shall be referred herein as "genetic vaccines". The question thus becomes: Was the implementation of genetic vaccines a crime against humanity, more precisely extermination?

Are COVID “Vaccines” a Crime Against Humanity?

The first criterion for extermination is systemic effect, as in harm arising from an organized, institutionalized system rather than isolated acts. Systemic effect is obvious, especially from the following evidence.

The second criterion for extermination requires proof that the vaccines caused mass death. Current evidence focuses on the mRNA type and is conflicted, some implying evidence beyond reasonable doubt about safety (for example Semenzato et al., 2025; Hallas et al., 2021; Michiels et al., 2022; Gargano et al., 2021; European Medicines Agency [EMA], 2021), while others indicating the opposite (ex. Fraiman et al., 2022; Kakeya et al., 2025; Smith, 2005; Kytö et al., 2013; Mead et al., 2025). It should be noted that this does not mean all evidence is contradictory, as studies can simultaneously show overwhelming benefits and overwhelming risks if they study different things. Nevertheless, proving extermination would certainly be complicated, unless many studies were proven invalid (Smith, 2005).

The third criterion is knowledge or willful ignorance, also known as deliberate ignorance or conscious disregard. Many people seem to imagine that a direct confession of evil intent is necessary, such as "I just wanted to kill millions of people". That is absurd. What is necessary, is proof of knowledge about outcomes, or alternatively willful ignorance about outcomes (ICC, 2021, Art. 30). Many point to internal communication made public as proof of knowledge, yet, to my awareness, those are mostly vague. Ultimately, willful ignorance seems to be easiest to establish. This would require showing evidence that the responsible individuals had access to credible, unresolved scientific evidence indicating the possibility of large-scale serious harm and death.

The fourth criterion is also answered by the third criterion, satisfied once knowledge or willful ignorance is established, since continued participation or enforcement under such conditions constitutes contribution.

Given these facts, proving the charge of extermination is improbable. Nevertheless, extermination may be the most difficult one to prove, and is not the only crime against humanity the evidence indicates. Other inhumane acts, especially forced medical experimentation, appears most probable. While “experiment” has a specific scientific meaning, here it means any kind of study, including the observational kind. If there existed credible, unresolved scientific evidence indicating the possibility of large-scale serious harm or death, and authorities nonetheless imposed coercive or compulsory use of the intervention, then that compulsion constitutes a crime against humanity. If such credible risk did not exist, or if use remained voluntary, it does not. Uncertainty does not absolve responsibility; it defines the conditions under which responsibility must be exercised with restraint, transparency, and reversibility.

What counts as coercion or compulsion? In practice, the criteria are familiar: mandates, employment exclusions, travel bans and other social or legal punishments for refusal. Those who imposed these forms of compulsion, assume full moral responsibility for adverse outcomes. This is why voluntariness is so important. If you volunteered to take a risk, then no crime against humanity has been committed against you, even though other domestic charges may still apply. A common assumption is that “something is better than nothing”, that “we had to do something”. That is simply irrational: Something is of course not inherently better than nothing, especially if there was evidence that doing nothing would have been more effective. Indeed, this heuristic appears to be the primary reason COVID policies were accepted at all.

People may claim that this behavior is “normal”. If someone knowingly, or through willful ignorance, contributed to a system that caused significant preventable harm and/or countless preventable deaths, and then claims that their behavior is normal, that claim constitutes a confession and self-indictment. Calling a crime against humanity “normal” cannot be purely descriptive if you participated in it. Calling it normal presupposes acceptance. Unacceptable things do not quietly persist at scale. How can something be frequent, standard, and ongoing, without being accepted? It cannot.

Investigation Is Warranted

In summary, was the implementation of COVID "genetic" "vaccines" a crime against humanity? Was it an act of extermination? That charge would be difficult to prove in court. Was it another inhumane act, such as forced medical experimentation? If the word experimentation is used generally, then that charge stands, provided that credible, unresolved scientific evidence indicating the possibility of large-scale serious harm or death can be proven to have existed. Naturally, I am not part of any international court, so there is little more I can contribute. Even if I had clear evidence, the problem is more fundamental than people disagreeing on evidence. The problem is that people do not even agree what would count as evidence. For example, are COVID "vaccines" actually vaccines? This is not a question I could answer even with all the information in the world, because it is an institutional and definitional question. The public was subjected to coercive measures while key classificatory questions were still unsettled, and while the authority to settle them was not transparent to the public. Evidence requires a structure for it to be coherent, and the objective of this text is to provide structure. Some will question whether my questions are legitimate, proving the lack of a shared structure to even ask questions.

The most fundamental misunderstanding clearly is "the data speaks for itself". That is not even grammatically correct. "Data" is plural, so the correct sentence would be: "The data speak for themselves." Nevertheless, this grammatical error displays the background category error, the idea that data are a monolith which can somehow exist independently. Science was supposed to maintain this rational fact clear, however, many so-called scientists call themselves "empirical", which usually means they also believe that "data speaks for itself". Then they would call pointing this fact out "anti-science", showing how science is being turned into politics. If nothing else, the universal failure of public discourse, especially about COVID, should serve as conclusive empirical evidence that data mean nothing without structure, without axioms, which can only be provided through rationality. Modern people simultaneously insist that "all is relative" and lament the apparent impossibility of communication. Some will think this "drifts from law into philosophy", proving the lack of a shared structure, as law without philosophy simply becomes "the data speaks for itself".

Indeed, this certainly distinguishes this charge from previous crimes against humanity, since such crimes are presumed to be obvious. Yet, there is no requirement for

crimes against humanity to be obvious. Furthermore, questioning itself being denied, should also be investigated as a complementary inhumane act, resulting in great suffering and assisting in the execution of the other potential crimes against humanity. Indeed, is there a difference between forbidding questions and willful ignorance? Forbiddance of questions cannot be treated differently from willful ignorance because, in the same way as pardons, that would undermine international law, rendering crimes impossible to prosecute because no knowledge or willful ignorance could be proven if organizations could simply deny questions from being asked in the first place. As such, proof of questions being denied must also suffice to prove willful ignorance:

- If institutions can block inquiry,
- then claim lack of knowledge,
- then mens rea becomes unprovable by design.

The objective of this text is neither to compile a list of suspects nor to assemble comprehensive evidence, but simply to explain why the public accusation that a crime against humanity has been committed, is reasonable, and therefore should be investigated as such. I did not personally send this explanation to international courts, a high commissioner, or other relevant organizations, as I do not consider myself the most appropriate person to do so. I never even accepted those so-called vaccines, not due to an intrinsic distrust of modern medical practice, but simply because I am afraid of needles... Nevertheless, this text is released into the public domain, so anyone could use it to compile evidence and communicate with the relevant organizations. There are no special requirements or qualifications to report a crime against humanity.

References

- European Medicines Agency [EMA]. (2021). Assessment report. EMA/707383/2020 Corr.2. https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/assessment-report/comirnaty-epar-public-assessment-report_en.pdf?r=artikellink
- Fraiman, J., Eviti, J., Jones, M., Greenland, S., Whelan, P., Kaplan, R. M., Doshi, P. (2022). Serious adverse events of special interest following mRNA COVID-19 vaccination in randomized trials in adults. *Vaccine*, 40(40), 5798-5805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2022.08.036>
- Gargano, J. W., Wallace, M., Hadler, S. C., et al. (2021). Use of mRNA COVID-19 Vaccine After Reports of Myocarditis Among Vaccine Recipients: Update from the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices — United States. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*, 70: 977-982. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm7027e2>
- Hallas, D., Spratling, R., Fletcher, J. (2021). Methodological Analysis: Randomized Controlled Trials for Pfizer and Moderna COVID-19 Vaccines. *J Pediatr Health Care*, 35(4): 443-448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedhc.2021.04.001>
- International Criminal Court [ICC]. (2021). *Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court*. The Netherlands: International Criminal Court. <https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/2024-05/Rome-Statute-eng.pdf>
- Takeya, H., Nitta, T., Kamijima, Y., Miyazawa, T. (2025). Significant Increase in Excess Deaths after Repeated COVID-19 Vaccination in Japan. *JMA J.*, 8(2), 584-586. <https://doi.org/10.31662/jmaj.2024-0298>
- Kytö, V., Sipilä, J., Rautava, P. (2013). The effects of gender and age on occurrence of clinically suspected myocarditis in adulthood. *Heart*, 99:1681-1684. <https://doi.org/10.1136/heartjnl-2013-304449>
- Mead, M. N., Rose, J., Makis, W., Milhoan, K. A., Hulscher, N., McCullough, P. (2025). Myocarditis after SARS-CoV-2 infection and COVID-19 vaccination: Epidemiology, outcomes, and new perspectives. *International Journal of Cardiovascular Research & Innovation*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.61577/ijcri.2025.100001>

- Michiels, H., Vandebosch, A., Vansteelandt, S. (2022). Estimation and interpretation of vaccine efficacy in COVID-19 randomized clinical trials. *Statistical Communications in Infectious Diseases*, 14(1), pp. 20220003. <https://doi.org/10.1515/scid-2022-0003>
- Rashedi, R., Samieefar, N., Masoumi, N., Mohseni, S., Rezaei, N. (2021). COVID-19 vaccines mix-and-match: The concept, the efficacy and the doubts. *J Med Virol.*, 94(4): 1294-1299. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27463>
- Semenzato, L., Le Vu, S., Botton, J., Bertrand, M., Jabagi, M.-J., et al. (2025). COVID-19 mRNA Vaccination and 4-Year All-Cause Mortality Among Adults Aged 18 to 59 Years in France. *JAMA Network Open*, 8(12): e2546822. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2025.46822>
- Smith, R. (2005). Medical Journals Are an Extension of the Marketing Arm of Pharmaceutical Companies. *PLOS Medicine*, 2(5): e138. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0020138>
- United Nations [UN]. (2005). Principles of International Law Recognized in the Charter of the Nürnberg Tribunal and in the Judgment of the Tribunal. https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/draft_articles/7_1_1950.pdf
- World Health Organization [WHO]. (2020). Calibrating long-term non-pharmaceutical interventions for COVID-19 : principles and facilitation tools. WHO Regional Office for the Western Pacific. <http://iris.wpro.who.int/handle/10665.1/14520>
- Zhou, Z. P., Chen, Z., R., Bandara, R. A., Duan, R., Cao, H., Liu, J., Hu, J. (2026). DNA-Based Vaccines: Advances, Applications, and Future Prospects. *Genes & Diseases*, 102025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gendis.2025.102025>